

Supplementary File 9: Additional Figures

Figure S1

Decrease in Cerebral Oxygenation in the Medial Prefrontal Cortex

Note. Box plots and probability density functions are displayed for each condition and sex.

Each dot represents an individual participant. HbO_2 = oxygenated hemoglobin.

Figure S2

Decrease in Cerebral Oxygenation in the Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex

Note. Box plots and probability density functions are displayed for each condition and sex.

Each dot represents an individual participant. HbO₂ = oxygenated hemoglobin.

Figure S3

Amplitude of Activation in the Medial Prefrontal Cortex

Note. Non-normalized data with an outlier removed. Box plots and probability density functions are displayed for each condition and sex. Each dot represents an individual participant. HbO_2 = oxygenated hemoglobin.

Figure S4

Amplitude of Activation in the Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex

Note. Non-normalized data with an outlier removed. Box plots and probability density functions are displayed for each condition and sex. Each dot represents an individual participant. HbO₂ = oxygenated hemoglobin.

Figure S5

Amplitude of Activation in the Lateral Parietal Cortex

Note. Non-normalized data with outliers removed. Box plots and probability density functions are displayed for each condition and sex. Each dot represents an individual participant. HbO_2 = oxygenated hemoglobin.

Figure S6

Amplitude of Activation in the Occipital Cortex

Note. Non-normalized data with an outlier removed. Box plots and probability density functions are displayed for each condition and sex. Each dot represents an individual participant. HbO_2 = oxygenated hemoglobin.